

Antimicrobial Activity of Crude Bromelain Extracts from Different Parts of Pineapple Against Selected Microorganisms

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Abstract

Bromelain, a mixture of proteolytic enzymes found in pineapple (*Ananas comosus*), exhibits antimicrobial properties. This study aimed to evaluate and compare the antimicrobial effects of crude bromelain extracts from different parts of pineapple (crown, core, pulp, and peel) against pathogenic fungi (*Mucor mucedo* and *Aspergillus niger*) and bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus mirabilis*). The extracts were prepared, and their protein content was estimated using Lowry's method. The crown extract had the highest protein concentration (115.83 µg/mL). Bromelain protease activity was determined based on casein hydrolysis and tyrosine release. Antifungal activity was assessed using the disc diffusion method for crown and core extracts, and the agar well diffusion method for pulp and peel extracts. The results showed concentration-dependent inhibition, with higher extract concentrations resulting in larger zones of inhibition against test microorganisms. At 100% concentration, the crown and core extracts exhibited potent antifungal activity against *M. mucedo* and *A. niger*, like that of the antifungal drug nystatin. The pulp and peel extracts demonstrated strong antibacterial effects against *S. aureus*, and the peel extract was slightly more effective. The extracts partially inhibited *P. mirabilis*. This research highlights the antimicrobial potential of bromelain derived from underutilized parts of pineapple, suggesting its therapeutic application as a natural antimicrobial agent against fungal and bacterial infections.

Keywords: *Ananas comosus*, crude bromelain, antimicrobial resistance, *Mucor mucedo*, *Staphylococcus aureus*

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Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increase in fungal and bacterial infections, which pose a significant threat to public health. Fungal infections are becoming more prevalent in individuals with compromised immune systems. Mucormycosis, caused by *Mucor mucedo*, is an emerging invasive fungal infection that primarily affects people with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, those undergoing immunosuppressive therapy, and individuals with hematological malignancies (Serris et al., 2019). Conversely, *Aspergillus niger* is an opportunistic fungal pathogen that causes a wide range of infections,

including aspergillosis, which is a serious and potentially life-threatening infection among immunocompromised individuals. These infections are often challenging to treat owing to the limited availability of antifungal drugs and the emergence of resistant strains (Musa et al., 2011). Consequently, there is growing interest in developing alternative therapies for fungal infections. Bacteria are also widespread. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus mirabilis* can cause severe infections, such as pneumonia, bloodstream infection, diarrhea, sepsis, and urinary tract infections.

Bromelain has garnered considerable attention for its pharmacological properties, including its antimicrobial activity. It is a mixture of proteolytic enzymes that breaks down proteins and is found in all parts of the pineapple plant (*Ananas comosus*), including the fruit, stem, crown, and leaves. The fruit and its processing steps generate significant waste, including the leaves, peels, stem, crown, and core, all of which contain valuable bioactive compounds because of their antifungal, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties. This study compared the antimicrobial effects of crude bromelain extracts prepared from pineapple crowns, cores, pulps, and peels. The extracts were tested against a range of microbial pathogens including *Mucor mucedo*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Proteus mirabilis*.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Bromelain Extracts

Freshly ripe pineapples were purchased from a local market in Chukwukwu, Gwagwalada, Abuja, FCT. Pineapples were washed with tap water and peeled. Subsequently, they were washed with distilled water to eliminate dirt and debris. The crown, core, peel, and pulp of the pineapples were separated from the other parts as they were the essential components required as the source of bromelain. Homogenization was carried out by blending 120.5 g of each of the washed crown, core, peel, and pulp of the pineapple with 70 ml of cold phosphate buffer (pH 7.0, 0.1M). The resulting mixture was filtered using cheesecloth and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C. The supernatant was collected using a micropipette and stored in Falcon tubes in a refrigerator at 4 °C. This supernatant was referred to as 'crude bromelain extract' (Abdulrahman *et al.*, 2015).

Protein Estimation

The protein concentration in the crude bromelain extract was determined using Lowry's method, which was chosen because of its high sensitivity and consistency (Lu *et al.*, 2010). This method relies on the principle that when proteins are subjected to alkaline conditions and react with copper ions, followed by the addition of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, a visually detectable colored complex is formed. This complex can be quantified by spectrophotometric techniques. Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) solutions with

different concentrations were prepared and mixed with Biuret's reagent, followed by Folin's reagent. After a 30-minute incubation, the absorbance at 660 nm was measured to construct a standard curve that correlated absorbance with BSA concentration. This standard curve facilitated the estimation of protein concentration in the bromelain sample.

Determination of Enzyme Activity

Protease activity of bromelain was determined using the method described by Cupp-Enyard (2008). Casein solution was used as the substrate and incubated at 37°C for 15 min. Then, 1 mL of bromelain was added and the mixture was incubated at 37°C for 5 min to allow for proteolysis. To precipitate any undigested casein, 2 mL of trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added. The mixtures were filtered, and the tyrosine content of the filtrates, which is proportional to the protease activity, was measured. This was performed by reacting the filtrates with Folin's reagent and measuring the absorbance at 680 nm compared to a blank sample. The increase in tyrosine relative to the blank sample indicated the proteolytic activity of bromelain on the casein substrate.

Source of Microorganisms

Mucor mucedo (obtained from a human stool sample), *Staphylococcus aureus* (obtained from a vaginal swab on chocolate agar), and *Proteus mirabilis* (obtained from a urine sample on chocolate agar) were acquired from the Department of Microbiology and Parasitology at the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital (UATH) in Gwagwalada, Abuja. *Aspergillus niger* was obtained from the Environmental Laboratory at the Sheda Science and Technology Complex (SHETSCO) in Sheda, Kwali, FCT.

Preparation of Culture Media and Subculturing

The culture media used for isolation was prepared according to the manufacturer's specifications. The bacterial cells were grown on nutrient agar in a petri dish for 24 h to obtain a pure culture. The inoculum of each bacterial culture was activated in a nutrient broth and prepared for susceptibility testing. The fungi were activated on nutrient agar and incubated for 48 h at 36 °C to obtain a pure culture. This procedure was repeated twice to ensure a maximum pure culture.

Test Organisms Preparation

A wire loop containing a 48-hour pure culture of each test organism (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Mucor mucedo*, and *Aspergillus niger*) was transferred and gently swirled into 5 ml of sterile nutrient broth. This step was performed to ensure an even distribution of microorganisms. The mixture was then incubated for 2 h.

Antimicrobial Activity of Crude Bromelain Extract

The antimicrobial activity of the crude bromelain was assessed in two ways.

- i. Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative (*Proteus mirabilis*) bacterial cells were treated with crude bromelain extract derived from pineapple pulp and peel. An agar well diffusion method was used for this purpose. Appropriate labeling was performed on Mueller-Hinton agar plates, and microbial broth cultures were evenly spread onto the agar surface using a sterile cotton swab. Wells were then created in agar, and varying concentrations of the crude bromelain extracts, an ampicillin positive control, and sodium phosphate buffer (negative control) were dispensed using a micropipette for antimicrobial testing. The plates were incubated at 38°C for 24 h. This allowed the determination of antimicrobial activity by measuring the zones of inhibition around the wells after incubation.
- ii. Fungal pathogens *Mucor mucedo* and *Aspergillus niger* were treated with crude extract derived from the pineapple core and crown. The disc diffusion method, specifically the Kirby-Bauer test, was used for this purpose. Paper discs were sterilized and then impregnated with different concentrations of crude bromelain extracts, a nystatin positive control, phosphate buffer negative control, and a neutral control. The discs were aseptically placed on pre-inoculated agar plates and incubated for 48 h to allow the formation of zones of inhibition around the discs containing antimicrobial agents. The diameters of these zones were measured to assess the

antifungal activity of the bromelain extracts compared that with of the control.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents data on the protein content of different parts of the pineapple (crown, core, pulp, and peel). The protein content was measured using Lowry's assay, which was also used in a previous study by Musfiroh et al. (2018) to measure the protein content in bromelain from pineapple core. The data shows that the crown extract has the highest protein concentration (115.83µg/ml), followed by the core extract (84.52µg/ml), peel extract (50.93µg/ml), and pulp extract (32.89µg/ml). This difference in protein concentration may be due to the distribution of tissues and enzymes within pineapple fruit (Rowan et al., 1990). Chobotova et al. (2010) also reported higher protein content and bromelain activity in crown extracts. Abbas et al. (2021) found that the protein content in the crude pulp extract was 170 µg/mL, higher than the crude peel extract which was 128 µg/mL. However, after purification, the protein content of the crude peel extract was higher. It is important to note that the concentration of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) used in this study was 1 mg/mL, which is different from the 100 µg/mL used in the present study. Using a concentration of 100 µg/mL has advantages, such as more accurate measurements, reagent conservation, minimized dilution errors, smaller sample volumes, and prevention of protein aggregation problems (Provost, 2005).

The protease activity of crude bromelain converted casein into amino acid products and peptide fragments containing tyrosine. The strength of protease activity is directly related to the amount of tyrosine released from casein (Cupp-Enyard 2008). These findings align with those of previous studies that investigated the protein content and enzymatic activity of bromelain (Chobotova et al., 2010; Ketnawa et al., 2012), contributing to a better understanding of this versatile enzyme. Proteolytic activity of bromelain can disrupt the cell walls of fungi, leading to cell lysis and inhibition of fungal growth (Schönbichler et al., 2020).

Table 1: Protein estimation and enzyme activity of crude bromelain extract

Bromelain Source	Protein Concentration (µg/ml)	Tyrosine Concentration (µg/ml)	Enzyme Activity (U/ml)
Core	84.52	85.66	13.71

Crown	115.83	75.20	12.032
Pulp	32.89	74.14	11.86
Peel	50.93	80.79	12.93

Tables 2 and 3 show the results of the antifungal assays, illustrating the effectiveness of bromelain in combating fungal pathogens. The study conducted by Raeisi et al. (2019) emphasized that the inhibitory activity of crude bromelain extract against fungal growth depended on its concentration. Musa et al. (2020) suggested that higher concentrations of bromelain might lead to more significant inhibition. The results demonstrated a clear relationship between the extract concentration and its antifungal effectiveness against *Mucor mucedo* and *Aspergillus niger*. The highest concentration (100%) in plates 1 and 3 resulted in an average

zone of inhibition of 50 ± 10 mm, indicating potent antifungal activity. As the concentration was decreased, the inhibition zones gradually diminished. The lowest concentration (25%) resulted in an average diameter of 8 ± 0 mm. These findings suggest that the antifungal efficacy of the extract is directly proportional to its concentration. This observation aligns with a previous study by Ajitha et al. (2021), who reported larger inhibitory zones against fungal pathogens with higher concentrations of bromelain extract.

Table 2: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of *Mucor mucedo* and *Aspergillus niger* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple crown

Sample	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	<i>Mucor mucedo</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
Concentration (%)		
100	50 ± 10	27.5 ± 1
75	31.5 ± 3.5	34 ± 2
50	29.5 ± 17.5	27.5 ± 2.5
25	8 ± 0	17.5 ± 1
0.0025g/mL Nystatin (+ve)	0	35 ± 1
0.1M Phosphate buffer (-ve)	0	0
Neutral	0	0

Plate 1: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of the *Mucor mucedo* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple crown. (F1 represents *Mucor mucedo*, A1: crude bromelain with 100% crown extract, A2: crude bromelain with 75% crown

extract, A3: crude bromelain with 50% crown extract, A4: crude bromelain with 25% crown extract, Ny(+ve): 0.0025g/mL Nystatin, P(-ve): 0.1M phosphate buffer and Ne: Neutral).

Plate 2: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of *Aspergillus niger* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple crown. (F2 represents *Aspergillus niger*, A1: crude bromelain with 100% crown extract, A2: crude bromelain with 75%

crown extract, A3: crude bromelain with 50% crown extract, A4: crude bromelain with 25% crown extract, Ny(+ve): 0.0025g/mL Nystatin, P(-ve): 0.1M phosphate buffer and Ne: Neutral).

Table 3: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of *Mucor mucedo* and *Aspergillus niger* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple core

Sample	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	<i>Mucor mucedo</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
Concentration (%)		
100	22±3	36±1
75	0	35±3
50	23±2	29.5±2.5
25	20±0	18.5±1.5
0.0025g/mL Nystatin (+ve)	0	35±1
0.1M Phosphate buffer (-ve)	0	0
Neutral	0	0

Plate 3: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of *Mucor mucedo* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple core. (F1: represents *Mucor mucedo*, B1: crude bromelain with 100% core extract, B2: crude bromelain with 75% core extract, A3: crude bromelain with 50% core extract, B4: crude bromelain with 25% core extract, Ny(+ve):0.0025g/mL Nystatin, P(-ve): 0.1M phosphate buffer and Ne: Neutral).

A similar concentration-dependent inhibitory activity was observed when testing the crude bromelain extract against *Aspergillus niger* (plates 2 and 4). Both the crown and core extracts inhibited this fungus, with the crown extract showing slightly greater inhibition at higher concentrations. Importantly, at the highest concentrations, the crude bromelain extract was comparable to that of the

conventional antifungal drug, nystatin. This finding suggests that bromelain extract, derived from a natural source, can be a potent alternative to synthetic antifungal agents. The ability of bromelain to combat fungal infections is supported by its ability to achieve high levels of inhibition by natural extracts. This mechanism aligns with the concentration-dependent response observed by Hale et al. (2005), indicating that higher concentrations of bromelain would produce more proteolytic enzymes for

degrading fungal cell walls. The concentration-dependent inhibitory activity observed in this study aligns with the findings of previous studies. López-García et al. (2012) reported the antifungal effectiveness of bromelain against agriculturally significant fungal pathogens, even though it was sourced from the stem. Although the source of bromelain may vary, the concentration-dependent response consistently remains a characteristic of its antifungal properties.

Plate 4: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of *Aspergillus niger* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple core. (F2: represents *Aspergillus niger*, A1: crude bromelain with 100% core extract, A2: crude bromelain with 75% core extract, A3: crude bromelain with 50% core extract, A4: crude bromelain with 25% crown extract, Ny(+ve): 0.0025g/mL Nystatin, P(-ve): 0.1M phosphate buffer and Ne: Neutral). The results in Tables 4 and 5 show that as the concentration of the crude bromelain extract from

pineapple pulp and peel increased, the inhibition zone formed around the wells also increased. This suggests that higher concentrations of antibacterial substances result in more effective antibacterial activity (Bernier & Surette, 2013). Higher concentrations of substances lead to higher levels of active compounds that act as antibacterial agents, thereby improving the ability to eliminate bacteria (Ramadani, 2013).

Table 4: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus mirabilis* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple pulp.

Sample	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>
Concentration (%)		
100	19±2.83	14±5.66
75	19±1.41	20.5±2.12
50	9.5±13.44	9.5±13.44
25	0±0	0±0
0.005g/mL Ampicillin (+ve)	22±1.41	0±0
0.1M Phosphate buffer (-ve)	0±0	0±0

According to Davis and Stout (1971), the response of bacterial growth resistance can be classified into four groups based on the diameter of the inhibition zone: weak response (≤ 5 mm diameter), medium response (5-10 mm

diameter), strong response (10-20 mm diameter), and very strong response (diameter ≥ 20 mm). Using this classification, it was observed that concentrations of crude bromelain pulp extract at 100% (C1) and 75% (C2)

exhibited an antibacterial effect on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* in the strong category, whereas the positive control fell into the very strong category. The 50% (C3) concentration of the pulp extract showed a medium category effect (Plate 5). Both 100% (C1) and 75% (C2) concentrations of crude bromelain pulp extract effectively inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, resulting in larger inhibition zones compared to the positive control (Rahmi et al., 2019). It was also observed that concentrations of crude bromelain peel extract at 100% (D1) and the positive control displayed an antibacterial effect on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* in the very strong category (plate 7), whereas 75% (D2), 50% (D3), and 25% (D4) of the peel extract showed a strong effect. A concentration of 100% (D1) of crude bromelain peel extract effectively inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus*

aureus, resulting in a larger inhibition zone compared to the positive control. Moreover, concentrations of crude bromelain pulp extract at 100% (C1) and 75% (C2) showed an antibacterial effect on the growth of *Proteus mirabilis* in the strong category, whereas the 50% (C3) concentration of the pulp extract showed an effect in the medium category (Plate 6). In contrast, concentrations of crude bromelain peel extract at 100% (D1), 75% (D2), and 50% (D3) showed an antibacterial effect on the growth of *Proteus mirabilis* in the strong category. The microorganisms exhibited resistance to the positive control (Plate 8). The varied response of *Proteus mirabilis* to different concentrations of crude bromelain extracts demonstrates the complex nature of bacterial resistance mechanisms, as previously observed in research conducted by Andersson and Hughes (2010).

Plate 5: Zones of inhibition of *Staphylococcus aureus* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple pulp. (B1 represents *Staphylococcus aureus*, C1: crude bromelain with 100% pulp extract, C2: crude bromelain with

75% pulp extract, C3: crude bromelain with 50% pulp extract, C4: crude bromelain with 25% pulp extract, Am(+ve): 0.005 g/mL Ampicillin, and Ph(-ve): 0.1M phosphate buffer).

Plate 6: Zones of inhibition of the *Proteus mirabilis* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple pulp. (B2 represents *Proteus mirabilis*, C1: crude bromelain with 100% pulp extract, C2: crude bromelain with 75% pulp

extract, C3: crude bromelain with 50% pulp extract, C4: crude bromelain with 25% pulp extract, Am(+ve): 0.005 g/mL Ampicillin, and Ph(-ve) :0.1M phosphate buffer).

Table 5: Zones of inhibition (in mm) of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus mirabilis* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple peel.

Sample	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>
Concentration (%)		
100	23±1.41	15.25±6.72
75	19.25±0.35	15.5±0.71
50	16.5±2.83	11.25±0.25
25	12.5±0.35	0±0
0.005g/mL Ampicillin (+ve)	22±1.41	0±0
0.1M Phosphate buffer (-ve)	0±0	0±0

Plate 7: Zones of inhibition of the *Staphylococcus aureus* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple peel. (B1 represents *Staphylococcus aureus*, D1: crude bromelain with 100% peel extract, D2: crude

bromelain with 75% peel extract, D3: crude bromelain with 50% peel extract, D4: crude bromelain with 25% peel extract, (+ve) control: 0.005g/mL Ampicillin, and (-ve) control: 0.1M phosphate buffer).

Plate 8: Zones of inhibition of *Proteus mirabilis* treated with crude bromelain extracted from pineapple peel. (B2 represents *Proteus mirabilis*, D1: crude bromelain with 100% peel extract, D2: crude bromelain with 75% peel extract, D3: crude bromelain with 50% peel extract, D4: crude bromelain with 25% peel extract, Am(+ve): 0.005g/mL Ampicillin, and Ph(-ve): 0.1M phosphate buffer).

Conclusion

The results revealed that the antimicrobial activity of bromelain extracts increased at higher concentrations, resulting in a stronger inhibition of microbial growth. These findings underscore the importance of exploring the unexploited

potential of different parts of the pineapple plant, such as the crown, core, and peel, for bioactive compounds, including bromelain. Furthermore, the varying effectiveness of bromelain across different plant parts suggests that its distribution and concentration may vary within pineapple anatomy. Overall, this study highlights the potential of crude bromelain as a natural and environmentally friendly antimicrobial agent that could be further developed into a therapeutic product for the treatment of fungal and bacterial infections.

Author contributions: Conceptualization, Dickson Achimugu Musa. and Mohammed Olumide Raji.; methodology, Mohammed Olumide Raji. and David Teniola Lawal; writing-

original draft preparation, Mohammed Olumide Raji.; writing-review and editing, Mohammed Olumide Raji. David Teniola Lawal. and Femi Ajibodun.; supervision, Dickson Achimugu Musa.; All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing Interests: No competing interests.

Funding: There are no sources of funding to declare.

Acknowledgment: Not applicable

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